

Summary statistics

	Number of experiments	Mean±SD	Statistical test; DF	Post hoc test
Figure 3				
3A	siCTRL: 3 siTDP-43: 3 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 WT: 3 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 K136R: 3	8.43%±1.84% 3.23%±2.75% 63.98%±7.5% 27.50%±0.47%	one way-ANOVA; DF: 11	Tukey
3B	siCTRL: 4 siTDP-43: 4 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 WT: 4 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 K136R: 4	64.41%±6.97% 24.70%±10.01% 91.01%±3.08% 64.37%±5.15%	one way-ANOVA; DF: 15	Tukey
3C	siCTRL: 3 siTDP-43: 3 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 WT: 3 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 K136R: 3	3.65%±1.32% 2.34%±1.12% 12.47%±4.9% 2.26%±0.84%	one way-ANOVA; DF: 11	Tukey
3D	siCTRL: 6 siTDP-43: 6 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 WT: 6 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 K136R: 6	91.08%± 0.39% 89.67%±0.73% 93.88%±0.59% 93.77%±1.06%	one way-ANOVA; DF: 23	Tukey
3F	siCTRL: 3 siTDP-43: 3 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 WT: 3 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 K136R: 3	92.44%±5.09% 69.55%±3.08% 79.93%±0.9% 79.6%±2.89%	one way-ANOVA; DF: 11	Tukey
3G	siCTRL: 3 siTDP-43: 3 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 WT: 3 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 K136R: 3	81.73%±2.92% 63.52%±3.72% 74.13%±3.14% 65.74%±1.4%	one way-ANOVA; DF: 11	Tukey
3H	siCTRL: 5 siTDP-43: 5 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 WT: 5 siTDP-43+Flag-TDP-43 K136R: 5	77.98%±5.32% 29.82%±5.05% 42.52%±4.6% 47.7%±10.32%	one way-ANOVA; DF: 19	Tukey
Figure 5				
5B	Flag-TDP-43 WT+YFP: 3 Flag-TDP-43 WT+YFP-SUMO-1: 3 Flag-TDP43 WT+YFP-SEN1: 3 Flag-TDP-43 K136R+YFP: 3 Flag-TDP-43 K136R+YFP-SUMO-1: 3 Flag-TDP-43 K136R+YFP-SEN1: 3	3.71%±0.93% 3.93%±0.97% 19.27%±2.77% 3.28%±0.59% 2.77%±0.74% 9.04%±0.74%	two way-ANOVA; DF:29	Bonferroni
Figure 6				
6B_SUMO-1	NT: 5 TS-1: 5	0.42±0.058	Student's Unpaired t Test; DF:6	N/A
6B_TDP-43	NT: 5 TS-1: 5	0.74±0.07	Student's Unpaired t Test; DF:6	N/A
6D_SUMO-2	NT: 4 TS-1: 4	21.65%±2.7% 37.25%±1.49%	Student's Unpaired t Test; DF:6	N/A
6D_TDP-43	NT: 4 TS-1: 4	20%±1.25% 25.5%±0.64%	Student's Unpaired t Test; DF:6	N/A

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Figure 7				
7B_SUMO-1	NT: 5 KCL 3': 5	1.41±0.15	Student's Unpaired t-Test; DF:4	N/A
7B_TDP-43	NT: 5 KCL 3': 5	1.126±0.058	Student's Unpaired t-Test; DF:8	N/A
7D_SUMO-1	C_KCL 3': 5 N_KCL 3': 5	1.69±0.21 1.5±0.06	two way-ANOVA; DF:5	Tukey
7E_TDP-43	C_KCL 3': 5 N_KCL 3': 5	2.6±0.161 1.34±0.074	two way-ANOVA; DF:5	Tukey
7E_SUMO-TDP-43	NT: 5 KCL 3': 5	1.56±0.065	Student's Unpaired t-Test; DF:6	N/A
7G_TDP-43	NT: 4 KCL 3': 4	20%±1.22% 58.25%±4.25%	Student's Unpaired t-Test; DF:6	N/A
7G_SUMO-1	NT: 4 KCL 3': 4	21.75%±2.59% 55.5%±2.59%	Student's Unpaired t-Test; DF:6	N/A
Figure 8				
8C	NT_N: 4 NT_N+C: 4 NT_AGG: 4 TS-1_N: 4 TS-1_N+C: 4 TS-1_AGG: 4	74,9%±1.22% 16.01%±1.84% 9.09%±2.21% 67.7%±1.37% 24.37%±2.28% 7.94%±2.22%	two way-ANOVA; DF: 23	Bonferroni
8D	NT_Diffuse: 3 NT_Puncta: 3 NT_AGG:3 TS-1_Diffuse:3 TS-1_Puncta: 3 TS-1_AGG: 3	44.21%±3.3% 25.05%±1.68% 30.73±1.64% 33.81%±2.05% 33.75%±2.54% 32.44%±0.96%	two way-ANOVA; DF: 17	Bonferroni
8E	NT_N: 4 NT_C: 4 TS-1_N: 4 TS-1_C: 4	35.89%±1.97% 64.12%±1.97% 32.85%±2.55% 67.16%±2.55%	two way-ANOVA; DF: 12	Bonferroni
8F_Aggregates	NT: 4 TS-1: 4	26.56±1.4 26.36±1.47	Student's Unpaired t-Test; DF: 364	N/A
8F_AGG Distribution	NT vs TS-1: <0.20 µm: 4 [0.2-0.5 µm]: 4 [0.5-1 µm]: 4 >1.0 µm: 4	NT vs TS-1: 63 vs 63 23 vs 22 9 vs 9 5 vs 5	Chi-square; DF:3	N/A
8H_Aggregates	NT: 4 TS-1: 4	26.13±1.78 21.63±2.13	Student's Unpaired t-Test; DF: 110	N/A
8H_AGG Distribution	NT vs TS-1: <0.20 µm: 4 [0.2-0.5 µm]: 4 [0.5-1 µm]: 4 >1.0 µm: 4	NT vs TS-1: 71 vs 73 20 vs 21 7 vs 5 2 vs 1	Chi-square; DF:3	N/A
Supplementary Figure 4				
4E	YFP: 4 YFP-SUMO-1: 4 YFP-SEN1: 4	16.4%±4.2% 7.53%±0.47% 19.9%±4.29%	one way-ANOVA; DF:11	Tukey
4F	YFP: 3 YFP-SUMO-1: 3 YFP-SEN1: 3	100%±0% 100%±0% 100%±0%	N/A	N/A